

ISic4292

I.Sicily inscription 4292

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

marble

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Original provenance unknown; seen by Houel in 1779; then lost;
residsovered in 1993 in work inside the Palazzo Vescovile

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Palazzo Vescovile

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI334903

1. ἄρχουσιν
2. [Σ]κρειβωνίοις Νωμεντανῶ καὶ Μοδέστῳ
3. vacat
4. ²three unedited lines follow²
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

PHI 334903

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 53.1010

Bernabò Brea, L., Cavalier, M., Campagna, L. 2003. Meligunìs Lipára. XII. Le iscrizioni lapidarie greche e latine delle isole eolie. Palermo. At 795

Libertini, G 1921. Le isole eolie nell'antichità greca e romana. Ricerche storiche ed archeologiche. Florence. At 220 no.22

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